

Synthesis and characterization of manganese(IV) complexes with tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane Schiff base

M. K. Singh^{a*}, S. Bhaumik^a and R. A. Lal^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Tripura University, Suryamaninagar-799 130, Tripura, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 003, Meghalaya, India

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Abstract : Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate reacts with tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane (ohthH₄) in methanolic solution in (1 : 2.5) molar ratio yielding the complex, bis[tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane]manganese(IV), [Mn^{IV}(ohthH₂)₂] and its reaction with other oxygen and nitrogen donors results the complexes of manganese(IV) of the compositions [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)] (2) and [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)(A)] [A = pyridine (3), 3-picoline (4)]. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, cyclic voltammetry, electronic, ESR and infrared spectral studies. On the basis of UV, IR and NMR spectral evidences, the ligand, tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylideneamino)methane, have been shown to exist predominantly in the quinoneimine form and acting as dibasic tridentate, tribasic tetradentate and tribasic tridentate in these complexes.

Keywords : Manganese(IV), Schiff base.

Manganese is known to play several important roles in biological processes¹ e.g. in superoxide dismutase^{2,3} and an azide insensitive catalase⁴. Manganese complexes in high oxidation state are potentially used as oxidizing agents, catalysts⁵ and electro catalysts⁶ for the oxidation of compounds such as alcohols, ethers and waters^{7,8}. On the other hand, manganese in photosystem-II has become of particularly interest where manganese in higher oxidation state functions as a catalyst for oxidizing two molecules of water to molecular oxygen^{9,10}. While EXAFS data¹¹ indicate that only N and O donor atoms are bound to manganese, there is no evidence for a manganoporphyrin centre in OEC. In the coordination environment of nonporphyrinic N, O donors such species are of interest in the biomimetic chemistry of the water oxidation site of photosystem-II¹². The elucidation of the roles of manganese in biological processes in general and photosynthetic system particular have stimulated interest in the formation, photochemistry and chemical properties of compounds containing manganese in high oxidation states. The coordination chemistry of manganese is dominated by stable manganese(II) and manganese(III) centres and a mononuclear Mn^{III} centre has been established at the active site of some enzymes that display superoxide dismutase activity¹³. The possibility of a binuclear centre in the catalase isolated from *Lactobacillus plantarum* has been proposed¹⁴.

In view of the above importance of manganese complexes in higher oxidation states, it was thought of interest to synthesize and characterize manganese(IV) complexes from polyfunctional tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane and its reaction products with oxygen and nitrogen donors. The results of our investigations are presented in this communication.

Results and discussion

The analytical and thermal decomposition data reveal the formation of complexes of Mn^{IV} of the compositions, [Mn^{IV}(ohthH₂)₂] (1), [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)] (2), [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)(py)] (3), [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)(3-pic)] (4). All the complexes are air stable and decompose above 300 °C without melting. All of the complexes are insoluble in water and organic solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, benzene and ether, sparingly soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, acetone and soluble in coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The complexes on heating in hot air oven show weight loss neither at 110 °C nor at 180 °C ruling out the possibility of presence of water molecules either in the lattice structure or in the first coordination sphere around the metal centre.

The complexes have molar conductance value in the range 14.3–24.1 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ region in methanol at 10⁻³ M dilution consistent with the non-electrolytic nature of

the complexes in the solvent¹⁶.

The complexes have magnetic moment value in the range 3.85–4.02 B.M., which are consistent with manganese(IV) complexes adopting a d^3 high-spin electronic configuration^{17–19}. The magnetic moment values of all of the complexes rules out the possibility of presence of any metal-metal interaction in the solid state of these complexes.

Tautomeric structure of ligand (ohthH₄) : The ligand tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylideneamino)methane is expected to exist in naphtholimine form as similar to *N*-salicylidene-glycine but a comparison of UV spectra of potassium *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate (λ_{\max} 415 nm, ϵ 8817 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 345 nm, ϵ 1006 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and potassium *N*-salicylidene-glycinate (λ_{\max} 410 nm, ϵ 985 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 330 nm, ϵ 9185 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) in ethanol revealed that these compounds exist predominately as quinoneamine and phenolimine respectively²⁰. The ligand tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylideneamino)methane also shows bands (λ_{\max} 400 nm, ϵ 1118 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 300 nm, ϵ 9656 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The band at λ_{\max} 400 nm (ϵ 1118 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) is characteristic of quinoneamine form of the ligand while other bands arise due to $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions²⁰.

The quinoneamine form of tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylideneamino)methane is further supported by its ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO-*d*₆, which showed clearly the presence of =CH-NH-C≤ grouping. The signals of =CH- and >NH protons are doublets centred at δ 9.11 and 6.80 ppm respectively²¹. The naphthyl -CH- protons in the ligand appear as multiplet in the region 7.20–8.23 ppm. Since even weak signals for naphtholimine form could not be detected in the spectra, thus it should be concluded that quinoneamine form vastly predominates in solution as shown below. Quinoneamine form for related ligands such as *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)-amines has also been suggested²².

Infrared spectral data also strongly support the quinoneamine form of the ligand. The spectra of tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylideneamino)methane showed a strong band at 1632 cm⁻¹, with no

other band at higher frequency in the double band region, may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of the quinoneamine form after considering the UV and NMR spectral evidences. This $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band position is much lower than their normal range and such low carbonyl stretching frequency cannot be accounted for adequately on the basis of conjugation and internal hydrogen bonding. Thus the contribution of the tautomeric form, naphtholimine, seems probable. As a result the structure of the ligand is interpreted as to exist in tautomeric naphtholimine form (I) and quinoneamine form (II).

The infrared spectra of analogous compounds such as 1-phenylazo-2-naphthalenol²³ and 1-nitroso-2-naphthalenol²⁴ also show lower carbonyl stretching frequencies at 1625 and 1620 cm⁻¹, respectively. Due to electron withdrawing capacity of naphthyl ring, the tendency to exist in tautomeric form is enhanced. The greater stability of quinoneamine form (II) appears to arise from strong intramolecular H-bonding under resonant conditions.

The ligand shows two strong bands at 3323 and 3180 cm⁻¹. The essential feature of these bands suggests that they arise from -NH and alcoholic OH groups, respectively. The strong band at 1544 cm⁻¹, amidst bands due to skeletal vibration of the aryl ring, attributable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$.

Tautomeric structure of ligand in metal complexes : The electronic spectra of the metal chelates reveal that 400 nm band of tris(hydroxymethyl)-*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylideneamino)methane is shifted only marginally. This is indicative of the quinoneamine structural form of the ligand in the metal complexes also²⁰.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of all of the complexes have been studied in methanol solution. The free ligand shows bands at 300 nm and 400 nm, which arise due to $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transition undergo red shift on complexation indicating ohthH₄ coordination to the metal center. The complexes [Mn^{IV}(ohthH₂)₂] and [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)] show a band at λ_{\max} 537 nm (ϵ , 1.66×10^3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and λ_{\max} 541 nm (ϵ , 1.78×10^3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) respectively in addition to a band at λ_{\max} 630 nm ($\epsilon \approx 1.30 \times 10^3$ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). On the other hand, the complexes [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)(py)] and [Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)(3-pic)] show only one detectable band at λ_{\max} 490 (ϵ , 2.31×10^3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and λ_{\max} 541 nm (ϵ , 1.78×10^3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), respectively. These bands are assigned to $d-d$ transition bands for Mn^{IV} in octahedral environment. The higher molar extinction coefficient values has been attributed to presence of adja-

Table 1. Analytical, magnetic moment and molar conductance data for ohthH₄ and its manganese(IV) complexes

Complex (colour)	Yield (%) (decomposition temp. °C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_B (B.M.)	Molar (Λ_M)
		Mn	C	H	N		
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH ₂) ₂] (Dark brown)	67 (> 300)	10.30 (9.09)	58.90 (59.50)	4.86 (4.63)	4.86 (4.63)	4.02	14.30
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)] (Dark brown)	65 (> 300)	12.00 (11.88)	56.90 (57.02)	4.10 (3.89)	3.12 (3.02)	3.93	23.0
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(py)] (Dark brown)	70 (> 300)	11.30 (10.15)	58.34 (59.78)	4.46 (4.24)	5.21 (5.17)	3.85	22.6
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(3-pic)] (Dark brown)	65 (> 300)	10.05 (9.89)	60.82 (60.43)	4.84 (4.50)	5.52 (5.04)	3.92	24.1

Unit of molar conductance is $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Table 2. Infrared spectral bands for ohthH₄ and its manganese(IV) complexes

Ligand/ Complex	ν_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\geq\text{C-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (alcoholic)	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (alcoholic)	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ (quinone carbonyl)	$\nu_{\text{s(COO)}}$	Pyridine vibration in plane
ohthH ₄	3322s	1632s	1544s	1140m 1109m	-	-	-	-	-
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH ₂) ₂]	3423s 3100s- 2528sbr	1633s 1593s	1493s	1081w 1036w	479m	565s	-	-	-
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)]	3429s	1623s 1593s	1507s	1056wbr	495w	560s	385m	1381s	-
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(py)]	3416sbr	1633ssh 1600s	1480s	1056w	483m	570m	-	1394s	652w
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(3-pic)]	3391sbr 3058s	1633s 1609s	1460s	1069m 1029m	481m	565m	-	1387s	650w

cent charge transfer bands which contributes to its intensity.

Similar studies have been reported by Sawyer and coworkers²⁵ and Pecoraro *et al.*¹⁷ in the homonuclear tris(glucarato), tris(gluconato) and tris(sorbitolato) manganese(IV) complexes of 1-hydroxy-2-(salicylidene-amino)ethane and related hydroxy ligand where a band is observed in the region 545–575 (ϵ , $1.508\text{--}2.380 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which was assigned to *d-d* transition. The higher value of molar extinction coefficients was also attributed to the presence of adjacent charge transfer band, which contributed to its intensity.

On the other hand, an intense band at $\sim 585 \text{ nm}$ (ϵ , $4.500 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) observed for Mn^{IV} complexes derived from catecholate²⁶ ligand and an intense band at $\sim 650 \text{ nm}$ (ϵ , $2.090\text{--}3.020 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) observed for Mn^{IV} complexes derived from 2-

substituted(salicylideneamino)phenol²⁷ ligand have been assigned to LMCT band on the basis of high molar extinction coefficient values.

Electron spin resonance spectra : The X-band ESR spectra of the representative complexes (2) and (3) were examined in polycrystalline phase as well as in DMF at RT. In the polycrystalline phase two broad resonances are observed, a strong one near $g \approx 2.0$ and a weak one near $g \approx 3.5$. In the magnetically dilute state the ⁵⁵Mn hyperfine structure is well resolved for the resonance near $g \approx 2.0$

Interestingly, ⁵⁵Mn hyperfine coupling for the $g \approx 2.0$ signals is equal to 94G. Depending on the nature and extent of distortion of the ligand field from *O_h* symmetry, the ESR spectra of a *d³* ion can assume different Mn^{IV} ion forms^{28–30}. The spectra observed here ($g \approx 2.0$ and weak $g \approx 3.5$ resonances) are characteristic of small

Table 3. Electronic spectral data and ESR parameters for ohthH₄ and its manganese(IV) complexes

Ligand/ Complex	Electronic spectral bands λ_{\max} (nm) (ϵ_{\max} dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	ESR data <i>g</i> -values
ohthH ₄	300 (9656), 400 (1118)	-
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH ₂) ₂]	296 (1770), 537 (1660), 630 (1300)	-
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)]	295 (2115), 541 (1780), 630 (1300)	3.879, 2.082 ^a , 3.572, 1.973 ^b
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(py)]	295 (1893), 490 (1310)	3.572, 2.095 ^a , 3.572, 1.967 ^b
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(3-pic)]	295 (2178), 541 (1780)	-

^aPowder at RT; ^bIn DMF solution at RT.

axial distortion, $2D \ll hv$ where D is the axial zero field splitting parameter and hv is the microwave quantum (0.31 cm⁻¹ at X-band). When D is small, rhombic splitting is necessarily very small, since $D/E \geq 3$, where E is the rhombic splitting parameter whereas the large distortion case $2D \gg hv$ occur in a number of complexes³¹⁻³³. The $2D \ll hv$ situation for Mn^{IV} has been documented in tris(dithiocarbamate)³⁴. The spectral features observed in the present study (strong $g \sim 2.0$ and weak $g \sim 3.5$ resonances) are characteristic of small axial distortion $2D \ll hv$.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectrum of the ligand shows two strong bands at 3323 and 3180 cm⁻¹. These bands are assigned to arise from amine group and alcoholic -OH group. Another strong band appears at 1632 cm⁻¹, this band is assigned to arise from carbonyl group of the quinone amine form of the ligand. The low frequency of this band is attributed to the presence of conjugation and internal H-bonding as well as contribution from ammonium nitrogen atom of the naphtholate form. This shows that the ligand exist in quinone amine form³⁵. The band present at 1026 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu(\text{C-O})$ which arises due to alcoholic -OH group. The infrared spectrum of the manganese complexes (1), (3) and (4) show a strong broad band in the region extending from 2500–3600 cm⁻¹ accompanied by several medium intensity bands. The appearance of several medium intensity bands in the region 2500–3100 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of strong intramolecular H-bonding present in the complexes. On the other hand, in the remaining complex (2) no bands are observed in the region 2500–3100 cm⁻¹ which rules out the possibility of existence of intramolecular H-bonding in the complex. A strong band is observed centred in be-

tween 3416–3426 cm⁻¹ and the essential features of this band suggest the presence of alcoholic -OH group in the complexes. This indicates that the ligand is bonded to the metal centre through some of the alcoholic -OH groups, while other alcoholic -OH groups remain uncoordinated either intramolecularly or intermolecularly H-bonded. The spectra of the uncoordinated ligand shows a medium intensity bands at 1544 and 1518 cm⁻¹ which arise due to $\nu(\text{C-N})$ stretching mode. Low position of this band is due to decreased bond order between carbon and nitrogen due to quinoneamine form of the ligand. This band is replaced by a medium to strong band in the region 1460–1507 cm⁻¹ in its metal complexes showing a negative shift by 84–37 cm⁻¹. This shows that the ligand is coordinated to the metal centre through nitrogen atom of $=\text{CH-N} < ^{36,37}$.

Electrochemical studies : The electrochemical properties of manganese(IV) complexes were studied in acetonitrile solution using 0.1 M TBAP as a reference electrolyte.

The complex (1) does not show any redox wave while complexes (2) to (4) show a quasi reversible one electron reduction of the Mn^{IV} complex with E_{RT}^0 in the region -345 to -380 mV. The peak separation between the cathodic wave and anodic wave indicates their quasi rever-

Table 4. Electrochemical data of manganese(IV) complexes

Complex	E_{RT} , mV (ΔE_{pc} , mV) Mn ^{IV} -Mn ^{IV}
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)]	-380 (194)
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(py)]	-352 (130)
[Mn ^{IV} (ohthH)(sal)(3-pic)]	-345 (100)

sibility in nature. There is no evidence for Mn^{III}/Mn^{II} couple for any of the complexes¹⁷.

The negative reduction potential exhibited by the hydroxyl rich Schiff base $ohthH_4$ complexes of Mn^{IV} demonstrates the ability of the ligand to stabilize the Mn^{IV} oxidation states. Mononuclear Mn^{IV} complex, $Mn^{IV}-(sal)_2(bpy)$ (H_2sal = salicylic acid, bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine) also contains an N_2O_4 coordination geometry. In the case of $[Mn(sal)_2(bpy)]$, the reduction potential is +440 mV (vs the standard calomel electrode (SCE) in DMF). When the reduction potential of the present study is determined in acetonitrile relative to the SCE, a value in the range of -345 to -380 mV is obtained. Even though the couples correspond to reduction of the neutral complex to the mono anion and both the complexes contain an N_2O_4 coordination environment the Mn^{IV} ion is stabilized by nearly 785–820 mV by $ohthH_4$ ligand. This effect results from the coordination of the alkoxide oxygen atom, which is much stronger Lewis base as compared to the carboxylate oxygen atom of salicylic acid³⁸.

Experimental

Materials : Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde were E. Merck reagents. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. Reagent grade solvents were dried by recommended procedures before their use.

Manganese contents were determined by a standard literature method¹⁵. C, H and N were determined microanalytically at SAIF, Shillong on a Microanalyzer Heracus Carlo Erba 1108. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a Faraday balance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. The molar conductances of the complexes at 10^{-3} M dilution in MeOH were determined by using a Direct Reading Conductivitymeter-304 model with dip-type conductivity cell (Systronic). Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-983 spectrophotometer in the range 4000–450 cm^{-1} in KBr discs and in the range 600–200 cm^{-1} in CsI discs. The 1H NMR spectra were recorded on EM-90, 90 MHz spectrometer in $DMSO-d_6$ respectively using TMS as internal standard. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Spectroscan UV-2600, Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Chemito). The EPR spectra of the compound in powdered form and DMF solution at RT were recorded at X-band frequency on a Variance E-112X/2 band spectrometer, using DPPH as an internal field marker. Electrochemical measurements were performed under dry nitrogen atmosphere using an ECDA model and BAS CV-IB cyclic voltammograph with

X-Y recorder model RE 0089. EG & G Princeton Applied Research. It is a three-electrode cell using 0.1 M TBAP as the supporting electrolytes.

Preparation of tris(hydroxymethyl)-N-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane ($ohthH_4$) : In order to prepare $ohthH_4$, tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (1 g, 8 mM) in methanol (30 mL) was allowed to react on refluxation with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1.42 g, 8 mM) in methanol (30 mL) for one hour. The yellowish brown crystalline precipitate thus obtained on cooling, was purified by repeated washing with methanol and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ (yield 60%).

Preparation of the complexes :

$[Mn^{IV}(ohthH_2)]$ (1) [$ohthH_4$ = tris(hydroxymethyl)-N-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane] : A 25 mL methanolic solution of ligand, $ohthH_4$ (1.40 g, 5 mM) was added dropwise with stirring to a 25 mL methanolic solution containing manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.5 g, 2 mM) at 60 °C, which changed the colour of solution from pink to dark brown. The mixture was filtered and the residue was rejected. The dark brown coloured filtrate was stirred for an hour maintaining the temperature at 60 °C which resulted dark brown coloured amorphous precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo* over fused $CaCl_2$ (yield 57%).

$[Mn^{IV}(ohthH)(sal)]$ (2) [$ohthH_4$ = tris(hydroxymethyl)-N-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane, sal = salicylate ion] : A methanolic solution of $ohthH_4$ (1.40 g, 5 mM) was added gradually with stirring to a 25 mL methanolic solution of manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.5 g, 2 mM) at 60 °C followed by addition of 25 mL methanolic solution of potassium salicylate (1.08 g, 6 mmol). The dark brown coloured solution obtained after filtration was stirred for an hour maintaining the temperature at 60 °C which resulted dark brown coloured precipitate. The precipitate was suction filtered, washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo* over fused $CaCl_2$ (yield 62%).

$[Mn^{IV}(ohthH_4)(sal)(A)]$ (3-4) [$ohthH_4$ = tris(hydroxymethyl)-N-(2-oxo-1-naphthylideneamino)methane, A = pyridine (3) or 3-picoline (4)] : The dark brown coloured solution, obtained by gradual addition and stirring of methanolic solution of $ohthH_4$ (1.40 g, 5 mM) to a 35 mL methanolic solution of manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.5 g, 2 mM) followed by addition of methanolic solution of potassium salicylate (1.08 g, 6 mM, 25 mL), pyridine (0.48 g, 6 mmol) or 3-picoline (0.57 g, 6 mM) and stirred for an hour maintaining the temperature 60 °C. The resulted dark brown coloured precipitate was suction

filtered, washed with methanol and dried over fused CaCl_2 (yield 65%).

Based on stoichiometries and physico-chemical studies octahedral coordination around Mn^{IV} have been proposed. The tentative structures of these complexes are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Tentative structures of complexes : (a) $[\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}(\text{ohthH}_2)_2]$, (b) $[\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}(\text{ohthH})(\text{sal})]$, (c) $[\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}(\text{ohthH})(\text{sal})(\text{A})]$, A = py (3), 3-pic (4).

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